

Measurement of Copper, Zinc, Manganese, Cobalt, Nickel Ion Activities in Aqueous Solutions by Membrane Electrodes and Determination of their Mobility Ratio

M. Adhikari

Clay membrane electrodes have been successfully utilised for the determination of ion activities of NH_4^+ , K^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{++} , Ca^{++} , Ba^{++} . For this purpose Padegaon Ca-form and aquagel Ca-form membranes are found to be the best. Mitra and Chatterjee have extended the use of clay membrane electrode to measurements of ion activity of copper¹, zinc, manganese and cobalt². In this communication, an attempt has been made to ascertain if some of the clay membrane electrodes used in this investigation³ could be utilised for measuring Cu, Zn, Mn, Co, Ni ion activities in solution and also to evaluate mobility ratios of selected ion pairs.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental set-up was similar to that mentioned earlier⁴. Results on the measurements of copper, zinc, manganese, cobalt, nickel ion activities are reported in the Table I. The calculated mobility ratios of the pairs, UZn/UCu , UMn/UCu , UMn/UZn , UCo/UNi , UMn/UNi , UMn/UCo are given in Table II.

DISCUSSION

The results show that the range of activity over which the Nernst equation is valid, depends, besides the nature of the cation whose activity is measured, on the nature of the cation originally saturating the membrane and the nature of the minerals constituting the membrane. Thus, it is observed that 0.5 μ size Padegaon Ca-form membrane performs well of the lot in the measurement of Mn^{++} in solution. Using this membrane, the satisfactory range of cation activity measurement is between 0.0001 and 0.0081 for copper, manganese, cobalt, nickel and between 0.0001 and 0.0243 for zinc. Similar observations were made earlier by Mitra and Chatterjee¹.

Of the pairs studied, the mobility ratio is greatest with Mn/Cu and least with Co/Ni. The order is UCo/UNi , UMn/UZn , UMn/UCo , UMn/UNi , UZn/UCu , UMn/UCu . The differences in the standard potentials of the pairs of elements in aqueous solutions⁵, are as follows: $E^\circ\text{Co}-E^\circ\text{Ni}=0.04$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Zn}=0.24$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Co}=0.78$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Ni}=0.82$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Zn}-E^\circ\text{Cu}=1.10$ volt, $E^\circ\text{Mn}-E^\circ\text{Cu}=1.39$ volt.

1. Mitra and Chatterjee, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1953, 1, 12.
2. *Idem*, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 751.
3. Adhikari, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 817.
4. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 569, 985.
5. Conway - Electrochemical data, Elsevier Pub., 1952.

This is also the order of the mobility ratios, as has been indicated above. It was suggested by Mitra⁶ and Bose⁷ that if the clay membrane is supposed to act in a manner similar to a metal-metal ion electrode within the validity of the Nernst equation, the mobility ratio may be related to E° values for the cation pair concerned, e.g., for the pair, $\text{Co}^{2+}-\text{Ni}^{2+}$, $E^{\circ}\text{Ni}$, $\text{Co}=\text{RT}/2F \ln U_{\text{Co}}/U_{\text{Ni}}$. The agreement in the sequence of the differences of e.m.f. values lends some support to the contention of Mitra and Bose, but a quantitative agreement is not to be expected because other parameters in the electrode reaction which are likely to be involved remain unknown.

TABLE I
Ion activity measurements
(mean values of observed e.m.f. in m.v.), Temp. 25°.

Membrane	(a) Activity of Cu^{2+} ion				
Inside soln. activity	0.0001	0.0003	0.0009	0.0081	0.0081
Outside soln. activity	0.0003	0.0009	0.0027	0.0027	0.243
Padegaon 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.2	14.2	12.0
Na-form	14.2	14.2	14.1	14.3	11.0
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.2	14.1	14.3	6.4
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(b) Activity of Mn^{2+} ion					
Padegaon 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.2	14.2	11.0
Na-form	14.2	14.3	14.2	13.6	6.4
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.3	14.3	13.8	3.4
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(c) Activity of Ni^{2+} ion					
Padegaon, 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.1	14.1	14.2	14.1	12.4
Na-form	14.1	14.2	14.3	14.2	8.5
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.1	14.3	14.3	14.3	7.6
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(d) Activity of Co^{2+} ion					
Padegaon, 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.1	13.0
Na-form	14.2	14.2	14.2	14.0	11.7
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.3	14.3	13.8	7.6
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1
(e) Activity of Zn^{2+} ion					
Padegaon, 0.5 μ size					
Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.2	14.2	14.2
Na-form	14.2	14.1	14.0	14.0	13.6
Aquagel, Ca-form	14.2	14.1	14.3	13.8	12.7
Theoretical value of e.m.f.	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1	14.1

6. Mitra, D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1954.

7. Bose, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, 3, 109.

TABLE II

*Mobility ratio measurements*Membrane used: Padegaon, 0.5 μ size, Ca-form, Temp. 25°.

Mean value observed e.m.f. in m.v.

Inside solution forms the (—) ve part of the cell.

<u>Inside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Mn ²⁺	0.0003 Zn ²⁺	0.0003 Mn ²⁺		0.0003 Zn ²⁺
<u>Outside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Cu ²⁺	0.0003 Cu ²⁺			0.0003 Zn ²⁺
Obs. e.m.f.	53.0	Obs. e.m.f.	42.0	Obs. e.m.f.	11.5
UMn/UCu	7.9	Uzn/UCu	5.15	UMn/UZn	1.57
<u>Inside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Co ²⁺	0.0003 Mn ²⁺		0.0003 Mn ²⁺	
<u>Outside soln. activity</u>	0.0003 Ni ²⁺	0.0003 Ni ²⁺		0.0003 Co ²⁺	
Obs. e.m.f.	6.4	Obs. e.m.f.	36.0	Obs. e.m.f.	30.5
UCo/UNi	1.28	UMn/UNi	4.10	UMn/UCo	3.28

Sincere thanks of the author are due to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee of the University of Calcutta for his kind interest in the work.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
92, ACEHARYA PRAFULLA CHANDRA ROAD,
CALCUTTA-9.

Received May 21, 1965.